
**INDIGENOUS STORYTELLING AND THE CHALLENGE OF
MORAL DECADENCE AMONG ADOLESCENT STUDENTS
IN MANYU COMMUNITIES, SOUTH WEST REGION OF
CAMEROON**

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Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the effects of storytelling on moral decadence among adolescent students from Manyu communities of the South West Region of Cameroon. The specific objective was to examine the role of storytelling to curb moral decadence among adolescent students. The theoretical underpinnings of the study was informed by Family systems theory of Murray Bowen (1978), Pierre Dasens (2003) Integrated Theoretical Framework for Cultural Human development, William Glasser's (1965) Choice Theory and Reality Therapy (CTRT), Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy (REBT) (1955) of Albert Ellis, Mediated Mutual Reciprocity Theory for Cognitive Enrichment of Therese Tchombe (2019) and African Socialisation and Emotion Regulation Adjustment theory of Emmanuel Tani, (2024). The study employed the sequential exploratory ethnographic mixed method design whereby, both qualitative and quantitative data were collected through focus groups, interviews, and questionnaires. A sample of 48 parents was selected from four subdivisions in Manyu Division. That is, 4 chiefs, 16 parents for interview and 28 parents for focus group discussions. In addition, 361 adolescents were purposefully selected from some selected secondary schools in Buea Municipality, located in the South West Region of Cameroon. Amongst were: Saint Therese International Bilingual School Buea, Summerset Bilingual College, Inter Comprehensive College, Government Bilingual High School Molyko-Buea, Government High School Buea Town, and Government High School Bokwango. An open-ended focus group and interview guide for parents, knowledgeable others, and a questionnaire for adolescents were the main instruments for data collection. Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 3.0, Atlanta, Georgia. Both descriptive and thematic examination was used. Descriptive statistics, frequencies, percentages, and thematic analysis were used to describe the results. The inferential statistics were tested by subjecting the data to analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple Regression Analysis to confirm the verified hypothesis. ANOVA and Multiple Regression analysis show that storytelling has a significant impact on moral decadence, with r greater than r -crit and the magnitude of impact being moderate. Given that the value for r (0.341) and r -crit (0.087) at an alpha level of significance 0.01, it is evident that storytelling significantly influences moral

decadence. Parents and other knowledgeable individuals, who are often the primary promoters and users of storytelling, should use this strategy more frequently with adolescent students. This approach can help guide their lives and instill essential competencies through culturally sensitive adaptations, thereby reducing moral decline. Counselors, whether trained or untrained, should also incorporate storytelling into their sessions.

Keywords:

Indigenous Storytelling, Challenge of Moral Decadence, Adolescent Students, Manyu Communities, South West Region of Cameroon.

Introduction

Traditional African people taught their young ones to be morally upright by devising effective and pragmatic ways of impacting certain ideas and values in them to mould them for personal development, leadership, and nation building. Thus, the saying “If you train only your child, the untrained children who are friends with your child can spoil your trained child”. Training the youth is a collective responsibility of society. In the past, parents took time out of their busy schedules to teach their children important values such as tolerance, respect, and compassion. Parents used to instil in their children the morals and values of their indigenous cultures and traditions, shaping their character and guiding their behaviour. Unfortunately, this is no longer the case for many families today. Parents often become overwhelmed by societal demands and the need for financial stability, which leave them with little time to teach their children essential skills and competencies for survival, as well as the proper moral values. As a result, this vital aspect of upbringing has been neglected, and many young people are forced to develop these skills on their own. They often look to friends and social media influencers for guidance in behaviour development, which leads to the imitation of vices rather than virtues, resulting in a decline in expected behaviour.

Adebisi (2018) defines moral decadence as a decline in the moral values of individuals and society at large. He reiterates that the decline of morality is very evident when he reports that a day hardly passes without reports of student unrest, sexual abuse, certificate forgery, drug abuse, and other cases of indiscipline across Nigeria. Observations show that most youth today exhibit negative behaviours not only due to societal influences but also because most homes have failed in their primary role of instilling socio-cultural values. Moral Decadence (referred to as MD hereafter) is an issue that has existed throughout human history. At various points, communities and nations have grappled with the problems of moral decay and deprivation. MD can lead to a loss of moral virtues, values, and ethics, which results in various immoral behaviours such as stealing, prostitution, corruption, delinquency, and drug use and abuse.

The consequences of MD undermine the value of education and academic integrity in institutions, disrupt societal peace and security, and foster indiscipline and anti-social behaviour (Nnamdi et al., 2022). MD refers to any action that contradicts the ethical values and norms governing individuals and the society. Examples include drug abuse, examination malpractice, dishonesty, truancy, sexual misconduct, disrespect for elders,

stealing, and more. These vices are often displayed by young people, particularly adolescent students, who seek the easiest ways to navigate their challenges. Therefore, it is essential to examine MD by reflecting on the past to identify effective strategies for reducing its prevalence and its impact on behaviour, academic performance, and the overall well-being of young people, especially adolescent students.

Adolescence is a developmental stage of human development where body features and sexual sensitivity are on the increase. In the years following puberty, adolescents face the task of establishing their own identity separate from their parents (Kroger, 2007). Adolescence is a period marked by change and crisis. The World Health Organisation (2012) defines an adolescent as a person between the ages of 10 and 19 years. Ogundipe and Ojo (2015) opined that adolescence is a period marked with increased self-awareness, increased sex drives, and a period for the development of self-identity. The hallmark of adolescents is that they want to act like adults and demand urgent freedom from their parents. At this junction, without self-discipline and guidance from parents and the elderly, they fall into life's wrong road. Idensi (2010) outlined the wrong life of adolescents to include academic underachievement, lack of respect for constituted authority, anti-social activities like indecent dressing, bullying, smoking, stealing, and immoral acts such as sexual abuse. If these behaviours are not identified and managed immediately and properly, it becomes challenging for these adolescents to come out of them. While some young people may adapt well to these changes, others may face negative psychological, social, and emotional difficulties. Therefore, the primary goal of adolescents is to make the transition from childhood to adulthood. Young people need to do this while dealing with biological, psychological, and social challenges. On reaching adulthood successfully and unscathed, adolescence is influenced by childhood experiences, environmental stressors, and hazards (Geldard et al., 2019).

Before formal guidance and counselling was introduced, traditional counsellors in Manyu communities instilled core moral values in the youth through various methods, including advisement, folksongs, dances, storytelling, proverbs, and initiation. Young people visited uncles, aunts, and grandparents for pieces of advice on how to live life. They grew up picking important values from these people and significant others in the community, which moulded them and built on their morality. This is not the case today; negative moral tendencies among adolescents are common. It is no longer an abomination to hear an adolescent speak back to an elderly person, hit and hurt friends and parents. There is no doubt that moral decadence has primarily replaced core moral values in present times, with vices prevalent in the community. Could it mean that cultural ways of bringing up children have changed, or the strategies parents used locally in counselling children have changed or are no longer impactful? Thus, the study sought to assess how storytelling is used to curb moral decadence among adolescent students from Manyu communities with the hope of proffering an approach by which it can serve as a vehicle for moral rejuvenation and an aid to curb MD in adolescents in contemporary indigenous societies and communities.

The Integrated Theoretical Framework for Cultural Human Development of Dasen (2003) addresses behaviour in the environment where the adolescent student grows. It focuses on child-rearing practices and customs; conversation, modelling, riddles, and proverbs,

which are important in performing chores and errands, and in learning and acquiring skills and competences needed for daily living. A human development framework like this is fundamentally psychological. It explains the behaviour of the individual and particularly of the developing child with focus on normal development and not on pathological conditions, which agrees with the basic tenets of cross-cultural psychology that human behaviour must be viewed in the socio-cultural context in which it occurs if we are to truly understand it (Segall et al., 1999). According to Dasen, the Developmental Niche (DN) is a system in which the child and three components interact coherently, although there are inconsistencies, especially under the impact of acculturation. As a child adapts to his surroundings, the niche also adapts to the individual, and it changes itself during ontogenesis. DN is an open system where each component is linked with other aspects of the more general environment, but these links with the macrosystem are more explicit in the ecocultural framework and in the ecological systems theory (Dasen, 2003).

The influence of modernism and neglect by most parents to handle their children's moral development is a cankerworm that this generation, especially adolescents, are faced with negatively. Parents have become working, and business-oriented parents (especially mothers) and this takes them away from their primary responsibility of child upbringing. Children and adolescents are missing out on socialisation and the right moral development processes and strategies which used to obtain in the past. Moral values have greatly declined, leaving parents and knowledgeable others to ponder over this decline endlessly. No doubt acts of moral decadence in Cameroon schools and among youths are alarming. A few cases mentioned below justifies the reasons why the researcher decided to carry out this research. The Cameroon Radio and Television (CRTV) on January 14th, 2020, reported a 15-year-old student of Form 3, (quartrième) who stabbed his mathematics teacher to death, Njoni Tckounté Maurice, at GBHS Nkolbisson in the Nation's capital, Yaounde. (Crtv.cm/202/01- horror at G.B.H.S Nkolbisson).

Again, the Horizon Newspaper in one of its publication's captions: Student Stabs School Principal. It reads: The social media was awash with news of the stabbing to death of another school principal in Yaounde yesterday afternoon. The principal of Yona school Complex, located in the Nkolbisson district, was stabbed twice by one of his recalcitrant students. The paper reports "this is at least the second time in two years that a student has stabbed a teacher in the same neighbourhood of Yaounde VI. In addition to the above, a student was permanently expelled for beating a supervisor. The scene of violence took place on Monday, 28 March 2022, at the Bilingual High School Nkol-Eton, while the teacher was trying to retrieve the mobile phone the student was holding in defiance of the prohibition instituted by the school.

From the above cited instances, it is evident that moral values are declining at a faster rate, and this is the main reason why this study on the use of storytelling to curb moral decadence among adolescent students is timely to enable every society to go back to their traditional orientations and revisit the values and strategies of the past that will enable a rebirth of top-notch morals for generation and generations to come.

Review Of Related Literature

Agha (2003) says an action is right if it leads to physical, intellectual, and spiritual development or to a more harmonious personal and social life. Society exists because men give up part of their modes of existence and agree to a social contract surrounded by values. These values, which are termed moral values, include but are not limited to faithfulness, patience, integrity, responsibility, public spiritedness, respect for human life, justice, fairness, and equality (George and Uyanga, 2014). Where these values are absent, the society becomes filled with vices and a decline in moral values, leading to the deterioration of societal values, generally termed moral decadence.

Adetayo (2022), in his study, assessed the causes of moral decadence, identified those to be blamed, and provided probable solutions to the menace. The results reveal that parental negligence, negative mass media contents, peer group influences, among others, are the causes of moral decadence and that parents are mostly to blame for the level of moral decadence. To curb this menace would require that parents should consciously contribute to the building of a morally viable society by instilling strong moral values into the children through effective parenting, building positive peer influence, among others, to achieve the best result.

Storytelling is a method of recording and expressing feelings, attitudes, and responses to one's lived experiences and environment (Gbadegesin, 1984). The function of storytelling has been identified as mediating and transmitting knowledge and information across generations, conveying information to the younger generation about the culture, worldviews, morals and expectations, norms and values (Ngugi wa Thiong'o, 1982; Asante, 1987; Kouyate 1989, Alidou 2002, Chinyowa, 2004). Yatta (2007) sees stories as primary ways through which a great deal of African philosophical thought, knowledge, and wisdom has been taught. For example, adults would gather youngsters around a fire at night and tell them great stories about the past that helped the youngsters to grasp the prevailing ethical standards of their community. Stories that personified animal characters were often told, and these stories, while explaining the peculiar trait of each animal, also transmitted the virtues valued by society.

The story about the tortoise and the birds, an Igbo folktale as recounted in Chinua Achebe's 1958 novel 'Things Fall Apart' in chapter 11 (pp 68-70) dramatises a moral: greedy tortoise, full of cunning' manages to trick the birds out of all the food at the feast, and for his selfishness he is punished. Tortoise falls from the sky, and its shell broke into pieces. The story explains how the tortoise got its physical characteristics and how it sometimes misuses its knowledge. The Tortoise can be sometimes cunning and malicious and may sometimes dupe and trick others for his selfish gain. The Tortoise is a character that children relate to. He is a rogue, but he is a nice, kind rogue. Achebe thinks that children don't trust the character tortoise, but they like to hear that he is around because they know that he is going to do something unexpected, and generally, he will be punished.

Through the process of dialogue, moral visions of a culture are transmitted by its social teachers; through storytelling, advice giving, proverbs, and taboos make a person realisable. It helps to trace the main lines of influence implicated in the African way of

converting a human baby from the raw material of heredity to a full-fledged mature adult human being in relation to others (Schneider, 2010). Through proverbs, taboos, and other storytelling practices, African children acquire common idioms to enable them to live and navigate within the culture and community.

Such practices and processes help Africans to know themselves as members of a community which includes the living and the dead (Bellah et al., 1985). Obiechina (1994) asserts that stories impact indigenous knowledge and enable the development of community values and cultural norms for the young. They provide essential information and tools in dealing with the world outside the community, where one is consistently exposed to pressures and to the conflicting worldview of the neo-colonial world and its attendant prejudice.

Counselling through storytelling has been described as both an ancient activity and an emerging or, maybe more correctly, a re-emerging conceptual model (Glossoff, 2009; Nystul, 2011). Jenkins (2013) opines that stories are central to our development of self-concept and identity, and how we distinguish ourselves from others. Furthermore, counselling through storytelling is a process central to our well-being and seen as both an ancient activity and an emerging conceptual model that finds its roots in some very old cultural traditions.

This is affirmed by McLeod (1997) when he observed that, as an ancient activity, storytelling finds its origin in some very old cultural traditions with ritualised ways of enabling individuals and groups to manage interpersonal tensions and questions regarding purpose and meaning. Nystul (2011) contends that knowledge gained from storytelling is very different and meaningful from knowledge gained through science.

Looking at some empirical studies, it is evident that storytelling influences adolescents' moral decision-making. Liu (2017) conducted a study to explore Chinese primary school psychological counsellors' understanding and experience of the therapeutic use of stories and storytelling. The study used the constructivists' grounded theory approach of inquiry and purposive sampling technique to sample the views of 12 participants (nine females and three males). The findings from this study revealed storytelling as a technique that should be used to facilitate communication between the psychological counsellor and the child and recommend that, in addition to story content, a relaxing and non-threatening atmosphere developed through storytelling can also help children reflect on their life situations. Furthermore, by telling and discussing a story, the psychological counsellors create opportunities for children to develop psychologically, emotionally, and socially. These developments enable children to reinterpret their experiences healthily.

Akingbe et al. (2020) carried out another study to examine the role of storytelling in the moral upbringing of the Nigerian youth with the aim of reiterating the significance of storytelling as a veritable conduit for moral regeneration of youth and children. The study used the quantitative research approach to study the atrophy of the dynamics of storytelling in Nigeria. Two communities (Iwo) in Iwo Local Government Area of Osun State and (Evbologun) in Ikpoba Okha Local Government Area of Edo State were selected for the study, and the population comprised adults, some of whom are custodians of Yoruba and Bini (Edo) cultures, as well as the youth. The study found that the art of

storytelling is dying off among rural people, while it has almost become extinct among urban dwellers. Unfortunately, the youths and children who should have imbibed the morals of storytelling have apparently taken to mobile phones and several computer applications as means of seeking immediate entertainment. However, most adults interviewed and those who responded to the questionnaire administered still identified with the art.

This finding shows that 91.5% of the respondents claimed to view storytelling as an important vehicle of cultural communication and education. Experience with the practice of storytelling was also attested by both the young and old in the society, as all the respondents who were 60 years and above noted that the practice of storytelling was not new to them. Thus, oral narrative (storytelling) is ostensibly declining among most Nigerians, though some people understand its usefulness and want it to be resuscitated. The study submits that the pervasiveness of moral laxity among youths in the country may not be unconnected with the loss of this traditional tool of moral education, hence the need for its revitalisation, and recommends the following: oral arts, especially storytelling, should be revived and given adequate attention to counterbalance the growing influence of the cyber culture. In resuscitating the African oral artistic tradition in contemporary Nigeria, it is strongly advised that the traditional rulers/titular heads in their capacities as custodians of tradition should, as a matter of urgency, encourage the revival of oral narratives in different forms in their respective domains and communities.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical underpinning of this study was informed by Bowens (1978) Family systems theory that places primary focus on exchanges of behaviour that take place in each moment of interaction between members of the family. The theory lays emphasis into the dynamics of family relationships and how they shape lives. By understanding these dynamics, individuals can break free from unhealthy cycles and create healthier relationships for themselves and future generations (Kerr, 2000). Similarly, Smith (2016) maintains that patterns of interaction between family members call forth, maintain and perpetuate both problematic and non-problematic behavior. Therefore, from the perspective of family systems theory, the family is seen as the primary relationship context in which individual character traits and ensuing patterns of behaviour are learned and reinforced (Papero, 1990). The interactions between family members are viewed as essential in understanding the behavior and emotions of individual. Conclusively, the growth of an individual strengthens the enlarge family circle through the interactions and relationships built over the years for positive change and emotional well-being.

Dasen's integrated Framework for Cultural Development (2003) situates the child's development and education in an eco-cultural context, which contains: the cosmologies, religions, and values that prevail in that society. The theory explains the behaviour of the developing child and the individual with a focus on normal development and not on pathological conditions. For them, human behaviour must be viewed in the sociocultural context in which it occurs if we are truly to understand it (Segall et al., 1999). Furthermore, it brings in various child-rearing customs and practices such as the use of narratives, conversations, storytelling, songs and dance, sayings, riddles, and proverbs (Shey & Lukong, 2018) which impact the adolescents as they interact and socialize

reciprocally with more knowledgeable others, parents, and younger siblings. Dasen's integrated theoretical framework is of relevance to this study in that it provides an orientation on the building blocks that incorporates an adolescent development to include the value placed in the processes that lead to the transmission and acquisition of competences from parents, the orientations from parenting styles and ideas and the influence of the social and physical setting (mesosystem) of the developing child.

The Choice Theory/Reality Therapy (Glasser, 1965, 1998) emphasises personal agency, suggesting that individuals are self-determining and can regulate their behaviour to achieve wellbeing. Choice theory highlights the need for individuals to develop supportive habits for their personal growth; these are known as the seven caring habits. Caring habits are embraced by individuals as behaviours they control internally. These include supporting, encouraging, listening, accepting, trusting, respecting, and negotiating differences. External control is experienced as having dominant controlling behaviours over others. People who believe they are under external control are convinced that they know what is best for everyone, including themselves. These behaviours are called the seven deadly habits and are exhibited by individuals who choose external control and become disconnected from relationships by acting in ways that include criticising, blaming, complaining, nagging, threatening, punishing, bribing, or rewarding to exert control. Both the caring and deadly habits mentioned earlier are examined in the counselling process concerning individuals' overall behaviour (Portrie-Bethke, 2011).

The Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy (REBT) as propounded by Ellis. He believes that most people are not aware that many of their thoughts about themselves are irrational and negatively affect the way they behave in important relationships and situations. If a young person changes a self-destructive belief and replaces it with a more useful constructive belief (rational belief), then they will respond differently to an activating event because of the new belief. Having behaved differently, there will be a positive emotional consequence for the young person who will be more likely to feel good than to feel bad, in the way they did when they responded in accordance with the self-destructive belief.

Tani's 2024 theory of African Socialisation and Emotion Regulation Adjustment focuses on the role of elders and parents' socialisation behaviours through the communal apprenticeship process and how it significantly relates to children's acquisition of social competence and contextually approved behaviours. For Tani, the theory posits that cultural values that enhance culturally acceptable behaviours are the first context in which children learn about emotions and serve as a rehearsal stage for children's developing emotional skills, with these processes enhanced through contextual processes such as guided participation, role modelling, and direct instruction. Furthermore, the theory postulates that early adolescence relies tremendously on emotional competence (the ability to express and regulate emotion consistent with parental/societal expectations and children's ability to understand the causes and consequences of their own and others emotion) which helps in supporting children's ability to regulate their emotions through indigenous socialisation practices such as proverbs, folktales, storytelling, legends and so on.

The Mediated Mutual Reciprocity theory of cognitive enhancement of Therese Tchombe (2019), focuses on cognitive enhancement of adolescents and places the locus of control on the internal (the learner) adolescent. She goes further to highlight that children should be intrinsically motivated to be involved in whatever learning because of the value of the knowledge to be acquired for solving problems. MMR explains the interdependence in mutual reciprocal reactions mediated by the learner and environmental contingencies, both human and material, to enhance actions to bring about sustainable development. Through explaining, questioning, illustrating, demonstrating, soliciting, manipulating, solving problems, supporting others, being collaborative in short scaffolding in shared responsibility, and eventually by demonstrating knowledge and understanding. MMR employs guided learning and encourages involvement that enhances the individual development of self-confidence and autonomy as the learner participates in learning. It further explains that the learner's cognitive ability to respond, create, innovate, and mediate others' reactions is driven by the interest generated on the task because of the values and relevance of the activities in daily life.

Statement of the Problem

Moral decadence among adolescents has become a growing concern in many African societies, including Cameroon, where increasing cases of violence, disrespect for authority, drug abuse, truancy, examination malpractice, sexual misconduct, dishonesty, and other anti-social behaviours continue to threaten social harmony and the moral fabric of communities (Adebisi, 2018; Nnamdi et al., 2022). In recent years, schools and families have witnessed alarming behavioural tendencies among adolescents, many of whom demonstrate declining respect for elders, weakening communal values, and poor emotional regulation. Reports of students attacking teachers and school authorities, substance abuse, bullying, cyber delinquency, and other forms of deviant behaviour have become common occurrences within Cameroonian society. These behaviours not only affect the personal development and academic achievement of adolescents but also undermine societal peace, discipline, and cultural continuity.

Traditionally, African societies, including the Manyu communities of the South West Region of Cameroon, relied on indigenous socialisation processes such as storytelling, folktales, proverbs, songs, dances, communal interaction, and apprenticeship systems to transmit moral values and shape the behaviour of young people (Nsamenang, 2005; Schneider, 2010). Storytelling in particular served as a powerful pedagogic and counselling tool through which virtues such as honesty, obedience, hard work, respect, humility, responsibility, compassion, and communal living were taught and reinforced (Yatta, 2007; Obiechina, 1994). Through narratives involving humans, animals, and symbolic characters, children learned the consequences of immoral behaviour and the rewards associated with virtuous living. Elders, parents, grandparents, and knowledgeable others used storytelling not merely for entertainment but as a strategic mechanism for moral instruction and character formation (Ngugi wa Thiong'o, 1982; Asante, 1987).

However, rapid modernisation, urbanisation, technological advancement, westernisation, economic pressures, and changing family structures appear to have weakened these

indigenous mechanisms of socialisation (Akingbe et al., 2020). Many parents are increasingly occupied with economic survival and professional commitments, leaving little time for meaningful interaction with their children. Consequently, adolescents spend more time with peers, social media platforms, films, and digital technologies, which often expose them to values and behaviours that conflict with traditional African moral expectations. The gradual disappearance of indigenous storytelling practices has created a vacuum in moral education, thereby contributing to behavioural disorientation among adolescents. Although modern forms of communication continue to evolve, the moral and cultural lessons embedded in traditional storytelling appear to be diminishing in influence and application.

Despite the increasing prevalence of moral decadence among adolescents, most interventions have focused largely on formal counselling approaches, religious teachings, disciplinary measures, and school regulations, with limited attention given to indigenous African approaches such as storytelling. Existing studies have examined moral decadence and youth behaviour from sociological, psychological, religious, and educational perspectives, yet there remains limited empirical evidence on how indigenous storytelling can specifically serve as a culturally grounded strategy for curbing moral decadence among adolescent students in Manyu communities. Furthermore, there is insufficient research exploring how traditional storytelling practices can be revitalised and integrated into contemporary moral guidance and counselling frameworks for adolescents in Cameroon (Liu, 2017; Akingbe et al., 2020).

It is against this background that the present study sought to investigate the role of storytelling in curbing moral decadence among adolescent students from Manyu communities of the South West Region of Cameroon. The study aimed to determine whether storytelling still possesses the capacity to influence adolescent behaviour positively, promote moral rejuvenation, strengthen parent-child relationships, and reinforce culturally acceptable values and social conduct in contemporary society.

Methodology

This study utilised the sequential exploratory ethnographic research design. The sample size of the study was 361 adolescents drawn from 6 schools in Buea municipality (3 government schools and three lay private schools these include: St. Therese International Bilingual Secondary School Buea, Summerset Bilingual College, Molyko, Inter Comprehensive High School Great Soppo, Government Bilingual High school Molyko-Buea, Government High School Buea Town and Government High School Bokwango). Four (4) chiefs, 44 parents, and knowledgeable others (KO). The chiefs, parents, and KO (48) provided data from the focus group and interview guides while the 361 adolescents responded to the questionnaire. A four-item Likert scale questionnaire was designed to collect quantitative data. The interview and focus group guides were constructed for the collection of qualitative data.

Research Design

This study employed the sequential exploratory ethnographic mixed method research design. The choice of this design was informed by the nature of the study, which sought

to explore indigenous storytelling practices deeply within the socio-cultural realities of Manyu communities while also establishing the extent to which storytelling influences moral decadence among adolescent students quantitatively. The sequential exploratory ethnographic mixed method design enabled the researcher to collect and analyse qualitative data first before proceeding to the quantitative phase. This design was considered appropriate because it provided a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation through the integration of qualitative and quantitative approaches.

The ethnographic component of the study allowed the researchers to explore indigenous storytelling practices, cultural values, behavioural expectations, and communal perspectives concerning adolescent moral upbringing within the Manyu cultural context. Through interviews and focus group discussions with parents, chiefs, and knowledgeable others, the researchers gained in-depth cultural insights into the traditional mechanisms used in transmitting moral values and regulating adolescent behaviour. Ethnography was therefore essential in capturing the lived experiences, beliefs, values, and indigenous knowledge systems of the Manyu people regarding storytelling and morality.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of adolescent students, parents, chiefs, and knowledgeable others from Manyu communities of the South West Region of Cameroon. The target population for adolescent students was 6,321 students drawn from selected secondary schools within the study area. From this population, a sample of 361 adolescent students was selected for participation in the quantitative phase of the study.

The schools involved in the study included Saint Therese International Bilingual Secondary School Buea, Summerset Bilingual College Molyko, Inter Comprehensive High School Great Soppo, Government Bilingual High School Molyko-Buea, Government High School Buea Town, and Government High School Bokwango. These schools were selected because they had adolescent students originating from Manyu communities and provided a suitable context for examining issues related to storytelling and moral decadence.

In addition to the adolescent students, the qualitative phase of the study involved a sample population of 48 participants comprising chiefs, parents, and knowledgeable others from four subdivisions of Manyu Division. Specifically, the sample included four chiefs, parents, and other community members considered custodians of indigenous knowledge and storytelling traditions. These participants were selected because of their experiences, knowledge, and involvement in the moral upbringing and socialisation of adolescents within the Manyu cultural setting. The combination of adolescent students and adult community participants provided the study with diverse perspectives on storytelling, moral education, behavioural regulation, and indigenous cultural practices.

Instruments for Data Collection

The study employed multiple instruments for data collection to ensure comprehensive coverage of both qualitative and quantitative aspects of the research problem. The instruments included questionnaires, interview guides, and focus group discussion

guides. For the quantitative phase, a structured questionnaire was administered to the 361 adolescent students selected for the study. The questionnaire consisted mainly of close-ended items structured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was designed to collect information on adolescents' perceptions of storytelling and its influence on moral behaviour, discipline, respect for authority, social interactions, and other indicators of moral development. The questionnaire enabled the researchers to obtain measurable data suitable for descriptive and inferential statistical analyses.

For the qualitative phase, semi-structured interview guides were used to collect data from chiefs, parents, and knowledgeable others. The interview guide contained open-ended questions that allowed participants to express their views freely concerning traditional storytelling practices, indigenous moral education, changing family structures, adolescent behaviour, and the relevance of storytelling in contemporary society. The interviews provided rich and detailed narratives that enhanced understanding of the cultural dimensions of storytelling and moral upbringing.

In addition, focus group discussion guides were used with selected parents and knowledgeable others to generate collective views and shared experiences regarding storytelling and adolescent moral behaviour. The focus group discussions created opportunities for interaction among participants, thereby allowing the researchers to identify common themes, divergent opinions, and culturally shared meanings associated with storytelling practices. The use of multiple instruments enhanced triangulation, credibility, and validity of the findings by ensuring that data were collected from different sources and perspectives.

Findings

Data collected from the field were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, Version 30, Atlanta, Georgia. Both Descriptive and Inferential Statistics were used. For descriptive statistics, frequencies, percentages, and thematic analyses were used to describe results and answer the research questions. For inferential statistics, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient Product Moment (r) was used to verify the hypotheses before subjecting the data to Analyses of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple Regression Analyses to confirm the verified hypotheses.

Table 11: Responses from the Open-Ended Item in relation to the use of storytelling to curb adolescent moral decadence among the Manyu people.

Major Themes	Sub-Themes
1. Learning is enhanced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -More meanings to different situations are portrayed. -Good lessons are learned. -More about the society is known. -Exploits good memories for different situations. -Correct behaviours are learned from mistakes.
2. Change from absurd behaviour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Common acceptable behaviours are copied. -Bad behaviours such as drug consumption are avoided. -Manyu children change to good behaviours.

	-Good morals are learned.
3. Societal norms are enhanced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Build a mindset of good characters of a modern society. -Manyu children distinguish between good and bad societal norms and stop moral decadence. -Values of good citizenship are learned. -Moral decadence is stopped. -Good traditional practices are copied. -Culture and tradition are well understood.
4. Christian values are learned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Righteous living is imbibed. -Sin as a reproach is discarded. -Stops lying because of its harmful effects. -Good life lessons and happiness are learned. -Teaches good morals like “Honour your father and your mother”, which are part of the Manyu tradition.
5. Enhances living together and collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Brings people to sit together, listen together and interact. -Brings family members together and make them know many things. -Family bonds are strengthened. -Family members take the challenges of life and overcome them.
6. Social Interactions are encouraged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enhances good interactions with strangers. -Transmission of cultural values, fostering empathy and promotion of ethical thinking is practiced and enhanced. -Cultural practices are learned and put in action as exchanges take place in a social gathering.
7. Plays Educative roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Good life lessons are learned. -Common acceptable behaviours are learned. -Values are learned and practiced. -Good peer relationships are encouraged. -Corrects the wrongs.

Results on table 1 show that the responses produced several sub-themes from which themes were generated. Respondents presented the following as the differences between modern-day storytelling and ancient storytelling. Parents rarely sit with their children to tell stories because they are involved with their jobs and other things that occupy them. Although this difference exists, respondents were optimistic that, if parents sit with them and tell them stories that can influence their lives with positive lessons and messages, life will be better, and challenges will be confidently faced. They acknowledged that the few times that they have been told stories by their parents and elders, it has left them self-confident with values and relevance.

Table 2: *Summary of Themes and Sub-Themes Generated from the Focus Groups' Responses on the Use of Storytelling to Curb Moral Decadence in Present Times*

Major Themes	Sub-Themes
1. Present day storytelling transformed into digital messages of love etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Storytelling have been converted to different digital forms yet portray a lot of meanings. -Conveyed to films, comedy, short videos, and stories with many lessons taught and learned. -Lessons of love for the family. -Lessons of love for the Manyu tradition and culture -Lessons of love for Cameroon.
2. Enhances teaching of ethical values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Different virtues and vices of the society are taught and learned. -Brings adolescents to taking decisions when faced with challenges. -Parents who sit with children teach them moral values through storytelling.
3. Parent-Child Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -It is used as an avenue for parents to have firm attachment with their children. -Children interact more with their parents. -Father and child bond or mother and child bond is strengthened through sitting and listening stories.
4. Educative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good behaviours are taught and learned. -Life lessons are learned. -There is a change in behaviour.

Arrey (2025)

The responses that follow were categorised from the interview conducted. The responses show that storytelling is a vital tool for the transmission of knowledge for individual flourishing. Parents indicated that the lessons from stories included love for the family, love for self and the community. It also taught lessons on vices, virtues and the consequences for certain behaviour patterns of the society and encouraged parents to always sit with their children to narrate these stories to them. They see this as the right opportunity to bond and build the right attachment with them that will lead to positive change in behaviour and morality.

Table 3: *Responses from the Interview on the use of storytelling to Curb Moral Decadence.*

Major Themes	Sub-Themes
1. Educative in nature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -They transmit information that is beneficial to adolescents. -Their education has moral values. -Teaches how parents grow up with good values and expect adolescents to do the same. - They transmit messages of good morals. -Builds up children to be upright, obey parents and friends.

	-Teaches good morals and instils fear in poor adolescents. -Educative to adolescents on how parents grew up and expect the same from them.
2. They are a source of knowledge	-They portray reasons for different happenings -Obedience, hard work, and good manners are learnt. -Lessons of good living and proper behaviours are learned from storytelling. -Teaches about sharing living together, love, and care.
3. A guide to uprightness	-Provide guidelines on how to behave. -Guides learning in the proper direction. -Coined to suit intended behaviour. -Formulated to suit different circumstances. -Informal for moral upbringing.
4. Encouragement for good behaviour as children grow	-Builds respect for parents. -Enhances moral values. -Build sup virtues in children.
5. Warnings for poor behaviour	-Warns about poor behaviour and its rewards. -Educates adolescents not to be stubborn. -They bring out lessons for poor behaviour.
6. Some have biblical values	-They teach Christian values. -They teach happy events. -They teach forgiveness. -Teach and maintain good family values. -They are imaginations of real occurrences

Arrey (2025)

In addition to the role of storytelling in curbing moral decadence, respondents to the interview think that:

- Parents should tell stories wherever they find themselves.
- Evenings are suitable for storytelling when everyone has retired and should be utilized.
- Tradition should not or does not change, so storytelling should be told in school, family, and society.
- Due to modernity, traditional storytelling should not stop but can be adapted to suit present times with its lessons undiluted.

Storytelling among adolescents from Manyu division impacts moral decadence through the following major themes: Learning is enhanced, absurd behaviour is changed, good societal norms are enhanced, Christian values are learned, living together and collaboration is enhanced, social interactions are encouraged, educative in nature, parent-child engagement is enhanced, they act as guides, they are a source of knowledge, encouragements to good behaviours and they are warnings for poor behaviour. This is supported by Nsamenang, (2005) who says that children learn from parents in three

ways: observation, imitation, and co-participation in activities. Through these actions (encouraging, recognising, initiating, responding, promoting, explaining), they make suggestions, indicate recognition, demand change of behaviour, enrich and enhance the reaction of young people.

Testing and verification of Hypothesis 1

Ha: The use of storytelling has a significant impact on adolescent students' moral decadence from Manyu communities.

Table 4: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Value from SPSS Computation, Version 30 on the Use of Storytelling to curb Moral Decadence

Variables	N	df	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r_{-comp}	r_{-crit}
			Σy	Σy^2			
The use of storytelling			6708	77032	53680		
Moral decadence	361	360	3264	33511		0.341	0.087

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

P = 0.01, r is significant

At an alpha level of significance, 0.01 (99% confidence level), the Computed Pearson Correlation Coefficient Value (r)=0.341 for degree of freedom 360. Its corresponding critical value (table value) r -crit = 0.087. Since r.computed value 0.341 is greater than r-critical value, 0.087, the null hypothesis is rejected following the decision rule. Inference made, led the researcher to conclude that the use of storytelling amongst adolescent students has a significant impact on their moral decadence. Since the r -computed value (0.341) lies within 0.334 and 0.666m the magnitude of impact is moderate. This is supported by Akingbe et al. (2020), who carried out a study to examine the role of storytelling in the moral upbringing of the Nigerian youth to reiterate the significance of storytelling as a veritable conduit for moral regeneration of youths and children in the quest for national development and the use of structuralism to explain that cultural elements operate in an interrelated manner. The study recommends oral arts and tradition, especially storytelling, to be revived and given adequate attention to preserve cultural values and history and most importantly, counterbalance the growing influence of cyber culture.

Tchombe (2011) highlights that children should be intrinsically motivated to be involved in learning because of the value of the knowledge to be acquired for solving problems. This will enable them to consider their socio-eco-cultural settings, beliefs, and values in developing their thinking, problem-solving skills, and their outcome. Tchombe's learning theory focuses on reciprocity as a learning process where a learning stimulus initiates a shared responsive connection between the child and the adult for sustainability and effective knowledge transfer. The Mediated Mutual Reciprocity (MMR) theory employs guided learning and encourages involvement that enhances the individual development of self-confidence and autonomy as the learner participates in learning. It further explains

that the learner's cognitive ability to respond, create, innovate, and mediate other's reactions is driven by the interest generated on the task because of the values and relevance of the activities in daily life. Therefore, because of the nature of storytelling, learning is guaranteed as explained by MMR.

Discussions

The results of this study are consistent with Akingbe et al. (2020), who carried out a study to examine the role of storytelling in the moral upbringing of the Nigerian youth. He submits that the pervasiveness of moral laxity among youths in the country may not be unconnected with the loss of this traditional tool of moral education and opines the need for its revitalisation. Furthermore, they strongly advised that the traditional rulers/titular heads in their capacities as custodians of tradition should, as a matter of urgency, encourage the revival of oral narratives in different forms in their respective domains and communities. Again, professional storytellers should be commissioned to go to schools, from the primary level, to narrate important tales to pupils and students. The results revealed that storytelling will impact moral decadence of adolescent students from Manyu communities positively, as respondents were optimistic that if narrated properly, on a one-on-one basis, timely and adequately, good lessons will be learnt from them.

Recommendations

The results of the study reveal the place of storytelling in our society, especially when it is rightfully used to impact adolescent students' moral behaviour. It is important that adolescents and parents spend time together and use the strategy of storytelling to teach them lessons that can be gained. Storytelling can become a standard for the enrichment of personality and an avenue to understand various personalities of adolescents to know exactly how to guide their thoughts and reactions. The study recommends that parents and knowledgeable others (KO), considered as the first promoters and users of storytelling, become intentional about its usage to avoid infiltration from other cultures. They should, as a matter of urgency, promote the traditional culture and norms of the society, encourage the promotion, restoration, and preservation of decency, discipline, self-control, and respect for elders and constituted authorities. Furthermore, they should be exemplary and reprimand those who promote vices and applaud those who promote virtues.

On the other hand, traditional rulers and chiefs should promote the culture and its virtues by resuscitating and enthroning the once cherished traditional value system that promoted healthy living and coexistence. This should be done by instituting and teaching TCS, mobilise the community for community flourishing, maintain traditional social norms and values hence fostering a sense of collective responsibility. Furthermore, as moral leaders who guide their people, preserving the local language alongside other traditional edifices of the people should be prioritised to avoid cultural erosion whose breakdown may lead to widespread behavioural disorientation among adolescents. The local language should be encouraged at all levels starting from the home to school and the larger society because it is the first portal for the execution of the right skills and competences.

Counsellors (both trained and untrained) should adopt the use of storytelling in their counselling sessions alongside other skills like active listening, empathy and unconditional positive regard approaches to build trust and rapport thereby creating open discussions that lead to collaborative, comfortable and therapeutic outcomes. In a nutshell, they should build cultural competence and sensitivity recognising cultural backgrounds, values and beliefs that will enable them to become effective and efficient avoiding the one-size-fits-all approach.

Conclusion

This study set out to investigate the role of storytelling in curbing moral decadence among adolescent students from Manyu communities of the South West Region of Cameroon. The study emerged from growing concerns regarding the increasing prevalence of anti-social behaviours among adolescents, including disrespect for elders, violence, dishonesty, drug abuse, truancy, examination malpractice, and other forms of behavioural deviance that continue to threaten the moral fabric of African societies (Adebisi, 2018; Nnamdi et al., 2022). Against the backdrop of weakening indigenous socialisation systems and increasing exposure of adolescents to foreign cultural influences through modern technology and social media, the study sought to determine whether storytelling, as an indigenous pedagogic and counselling strategy, still possesses the capacity to shape positive behaviour and moral consciousness among young people.

The findings of the study revealed that storytelling remains a highly relevant and culturally significant tool for moral education and adolescent socialisation within Manyu communities. Evidence from interviews, focus group discussions, and questionnaire responses demonstrated that storytelling contributes significantly to the transmission of societal norms, ethical values, communal identity, Christian virtues, and acceptable behavioural standards. Participants strongly affirmed that storytelling teaches adolescents lessons related to honesty, obedience, hard work, respect for elders, cooperation, empathy, peaceful coexistence, and responsibility. Through stories, adolescents are exposed to the consequences of immoral behaviours and the rewards associated with virtuous living. These findings corroborate earlier assertions by Yatta (2007), Obiechina (1994), and Ngugi wa Thiong'o (1982), who emphasised that African storytelling functions as a powerful mechanism for transmitting cultural wisdom, morality, and indigenous knowledge across generations.

The study further established that storytelling enhances social interaction, strengthens parent-child relationships, promotes family bonding, and creates opportunities for emotional learning and behavioural guidance. Parents and knowledgeable others indicated that storytelling sessions provide avenues through which adolescents interact meaningfully with elders and acquire culturally acceptable ways of thinking and behaving. This aligns with Nsamenang's (2005) position that African children learn through observation, imitation, co-participation, and guided interaction within communal settings. The findings equally support Tchombe's (2011; 2019) Mediated Mutual Reciprocity theory, which emphasises reciprocal learning, guided participation, and meaningful interaction as essential components of cognitive and behavioural development.

Quantitative findings from the study revealed that storytelling has a statistically significant influence on moral decadence among adolescent students. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis produced an r -computed value of 0.341, which was greater than the critical value of 0.087 at the 0.01 level of significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The findings therefore confirmed that storytelling significantly influences adolescent moral behaviour, with the magnitude of influence being moderate. This implies that storytelling possesses considerable potential as a culturally grounded intervention strategy for reducing moral decadence among adolescents when effectively utilised within homes, schools, and communities. The findings are consistent with the study of Akingbe et al. (2020), who argued that the decline of storytelling practices contributes significantly to moral laxity among youths and recommended the revitalisation of oral traditions as instruments for moral regeneration.

The study also revealed that despite the continued relevance of storytelling, modernisation, urbanisation, technological advancement, and changing family structures have contributed to the gradual decline of indigenous storytelling practices. Many parents no longer dedicate sufficient time to interact with their children due to economic pressures and changing lifestyles. Consequently, adolescents increasingly turn to peers, social media, films, and digital platforms for guidance and entertainment, often exposing them to values that contradict African communal ethics and behavioural expectations. The erosion of indigenous storytelling traditions therefore reflects a broader weakening of African indigenous systems of moral education and cultural continuity.

Theoretically, the study validates the relevance of the Family Systems Theory of Bowen (1978), Dasen's Integrated Framework for Cultural Human Development (2003), Choice Theory and Reality Therapy of Glasser (1965; 1998), Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy of Ellis (1955), Tchombe's Mediated Mutual Reciprocity Theory (2019), and Tani's African Socialisation and Emotion Regulation Adjustment Theory (2024). These theories collectively demonstrate that adolescent behaviour is shaped within social, cultural, emotional, and relational contexts, and that indigenous cultural practices such as storytelling remain essential in promoting emotional regulation, behavioural adjustment, identity formation, and moral competence among young people.

Conclusively, the study affirms that storytelling is not merely an entertainment activity but an indigenous educational, psychological, and counselling instrument capable of contributing meaningfully to adolescent moral development and social transformation. The revitalisation and integration of storytelling into contemporary parenting practices, counselling programmes, schools, and community initiatives could serve as an important strategy for moral rejuvenation and the preservation of African cultural identity. The study therefore calls for intentional efforts by parents, educators, counsellors, traditional rulers, and policymakers to preserve and promote indigenous storytelling traditions as sustainable tools for addressing moral decadence and strengthening the moral foundations of future generations in Cameroon and Africa at large.

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